

CO-CONSTRUCTION WORKSHOP REPORT

Initiative One Forest Vision (OFVi)

Democratic Republic of the Congo

Financial Support

1.	PARTICIPANTS	3
1.1.	ROUND TABLE PARTICIPANTS.....	3
1.2.	ORGANIZING COMMITTEE	4
2.	CONTEXT	5
3.	THE KINSHASA CO-CONSTRUCTION WORKSHOP	ERREUR ! SIGNET NON DEFINI.
3.1.	OBJECTIVES	5
3.2.	PROGRAMME	6
3.3.	ROUND TABLES	8
4.	CO-CONSTRUCTION WORKSHOP METHODOLOGY	8
4.1.	AGILE SCIENTIFIC CO-CONSTRUCTION STRATEGY: WHY THIS METHOD?.....	ERREUR ! SIGNET NON DEFINI.
4.2.	A METHOD BASED ON THREE COMPLEMENTARY BUILDING BLOCKS	ERREUR ! SIGNET NON DEFINI.
4.3.	WHAT THE WORKSHOP SHOULD PRODUCE	ERREUR ! SIGNET NON DEFINI.
5.	RESULTS FOR TABLE A: “CLIMATE, WATER AND CARBON CYCLES: ISSUES AND MEASUREMENT TOOLS”	10
5.1.	PARTICIPANTS.....	11
5.2.	VALUE PROPOSITIONS	12
5.3.	BENEFICIARIES	ERREUR ! SIGNET NON DEFINI.
5.4.	KEY ACTIVITIES.....	ERREUR ! SIGNET NON DEFINI.
5.5.	KEY RESOURCES	ERREUR ! SIGNET NON DEFINI.
5.6.	KEY PARTNERS	ERREUR ! SIGNET NON DEFINI.
5.7.	RELATIONSHIPS	13
5.8.	DISSEMINATION CHANNELS	13
5.9.	EXPECTED IMPACTS.....	13
5.10.	OKR: OBJECTIVES AND KEY RESULTS.....	14
5.11.	COST STRUCTURE	15
5.12.	ROADMAP — NEXT STEPS	16
6.	RESULTS FOR TABLE B: “ ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION: FAUNA, FLORA AND HABITATS ”	16
6.1.	PARTICIPANTS	16
6.2.	VALUE PROPOSITIONS	17
6.3.	BENEFICIARIES	18
6.4.	KEY ACTIVITIES.....	18
6.5.	KEY RESOURCES	19
6.6.	KEY PARTNERS	19
6.7.	RELATIONSHIPS	19
6.8.	DISSEMINATION CHANNELS	19
6.9.	EXPECTED IMPACTS.....	19
6.10.	OKR: OBJECTIVES AND KEY RESULTS.....	20
6.11.	COST STRUCTURE	21
6.12.	ROADMAP — NEXT STEPS	21
7.	RESULTS FOR TABLE C: “ FORESTRY, AGRICULTURE AND THE SCIENCE-SOCIETY LINK: TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE MODELS ”	22
7.1.	PARTICIPANTS.....	22
7.2.	VALUE PROPOSITIONS	23
7.3.	BENEFICIARIES	23
7.4.	KEY ACTIVITIES.....	23
7.5.	KEY RESOURCES	23
7.6.	KEY PARTNERS	24
7.7.	RELATIONSHIPS	24
7.8.	DISSEMINATION CHANNELS	24
7.9.	EXPECTED IMPACTS.....	25
7.10.	PRIORITY RESEARCH QUESTIONS	25
7.11.	COST STRUCTURE	25
7.12.	ROADMAP — NEXT STEPS	25
8.	ANNEXES	27
8.1.	ANNEX 1: LOCATION OF TABLE A SITES	27
8.2.	ANNEX 2: LOCATION OF TABLE B SITES.....	27
8.3.	ANNEX 3: COST CATEGORIES TO CONSIDER FOR COST STRUCTURING.....	33

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2. Context

The Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework sets the objective of protecting at least 30% of terrestrial and marine areas by 2030. However, existing market-based mechanisms and current carbon price levels remain insufficient, on their own, to support large-scale conservation efforts. In this context, *Country Packages* have emerged as a structuring instrument for international cooperation, designed to support countries in conserving major forest and wetland ecosystems while enabling development trajectories compatible with climate and biodiversity objectives. These packages rely on the mobilization of public, private, multilateral, and philanthropic financing, as well as on partnerships between governments, public institutions, donors, NGOs, and private-sector actors.

Within this framework, the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) announced, at COP28 in Dubai in December 2023, the launch of a Country Package aimed at supporting the implementation of a “New Climate Economy”, in collaboration with several international partners. These include France, Germany, the United States, the United Kingdom, the Bezos Earth Fund, and the Country Package seed fund managed by Conservation International. The initiative seeks to reconcile the protection of forests, peatlands, and key biodiversity areas with the development of sustainable economic activities, for the benefit of local populations.

The DRC Country Package is structured around three main pillars:

- **Conservation and sustainable management of forests, peatlands, and high-biodiversity areas**, with strong involvement of local communities,
- **Development of economic sectors compatible with forest conservation**, including sustainable agriculture, sustainable forestry, timber processing, forest plantations, renewable energy, clean cooking solutions, and ecotourism,
- **Establishment of a robust national policy and institutional framework** for the development of high-integrity carbon credits, ensuring both environmental and social integrity.

An initial financing envelope of USD 62 million has been announced to initiate this process.

This international framework is directly aligned with several national priorities and initiatives led by the DRC. These include “*La Forêt c’est nous*”, which emphasizes national and community ownership of forest-related issues; *the Green Corridor (Couloir Vert)*, which proposes a large-scale articulation between conservation, land-use planning, and development; and GEO-RDC, which contributes to strengthening national capacities in Earth observation, spatial monitoring, and the production of strategic data to support public policy. Together, these initiatives reflect the country’s ambition to define a national trajectory that reconciles sovereignty, conservation, and development.

As part of the scientific support and capacity-building components associated with Country Packages involving France, a consortium of French research institutions — including the CEA, Cirad, CNRS, INRAE, IRD, and MNHN — launched the One Forest Vision (OFVi) initiative during the One Forest Summit held in Libreville in March 2023. This initiative is supported by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research and the Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs.

The objective of OFVi is to provide scientific support to countries hosting major tropical forest basins, in order to improve knowledge and conservation of forest carbon stocks, wetlands, and biodiversity. The initiative is structured around several scientific pillars, including landscape-scale carbon and biodiversity dynamics, large-scale carbon modelling, remote sensing and artificial intelligence, and the human and social sciences. These are supported by a data management platform and complemented by two transversal pillars dedicated to co-construction with national partners and capacity building. The funding provided by the Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs specifically targets countries engaged in a Country Package dynamic, including the DRC.

In the Congolese context, OFVi is intended to play a structuring role by providing the scientific and technical backbone required for the implementation of the DRC Country Package. While the latter establishes an ambitious strategic and financial framework, it does not, on its own, define the scientific content, observation systems, research priorities, or training and data production mechanisms necessary for effective implementation. OFVi directly addresses this gap by supporting the development of targeted research projects, doctoral and postdoctoral training programmes, environmental monitoring systems, and a comprehensive strategy for data management and valorisation.

3. The Kinshasa co-construction workshop

3.1. Objectives

The co-construction workshop was held in Kinshasa (DRC) from 31 March to 1 April 2026. It brought together approximately sixty participants, primarily from Congolese and French scientific communities, as well as representatives of partner institutions engaged in climate, biodiversity, and development issues.

The workshop forms part of the dynamic initiated following the announcement of the DRC Country Package at COP28. Its primary objective was to operationalize the scientific and capacity-building components of the Country Package, in close articulation with the One Forest Vision (OFVi) initiative. In a context where the Country Package provides primarily a political and financial framework, the workshop aimed to translate this framework into a structured, coherent, and nationally anchored scientific programme.

The overarching objective was to co-construct an integrated vision of research and training needs to:

- improve the characterization of the dynamics, diversity, and functioning of forest and wetland ecosystems in the DRC,
- quantify the climatic and anthropogenic pressures affecting these ecosystems,
- strengthen the capacity of national stakeholders to produce, manage, and mobilize scientific knowledge in support of public decision-making (conservation, sustainable management, carbon policies, and land-use planning).

The workshop mobilized a structured co-construction methodology inspired by approaches previously implemented in Gabon, combining Agile principles, Design Thinking, and Lean Startup frameworks. This approach enabled discussions to be organized around operational objectives, translated into Objectives and Key Results (OKR), thereby facilitating the emergence of concrete, prioritized, and directly actionable proposals.

Beyond scientific discussions, the workshop also served as a platform for convergence between national and international stakeholders. It contributed to:

- clarifying respective roles and levels of engagement,
- identifying complementarities between existing national initiatives (notably “La Forêt c’est nous”, the Green Corridor, and GEO-RDC),
- establishing the foundations for a coordinated structuring of research and training activities over the coming years.

The workshop specifically enabled participants to:

- refine expectations in terms of research and capacity building within the Country Package framework,
- identify national scientific priorities related to carbon, biodiversity, hydrology, and land use,

- characterize needs in human resources, infrastructure, and equipment required to implement these priorities,
- define intervention axes consistent with national public policies and international funding mechanisms,
- outline a scientific programme structured around targeted research projects and doctoral/postdoctoral training,
- lay the foundations for a strategy for environmental data management, sharing, and valorisation.

As such, the Kinshasa workshop represents a key structuring milestone in the operational implementation of the DRC Country Package. It provides the first elements of scientific structuring required for its success and confirms the role of the OFVi initiative as an interface between political and financial ambitions and their translation into robust scientific programmes capable of generating actionable, transferable, and sustainable knowledge.

3.2. Programme

The co-construction workshop was structured over two days, combining high-level institutional engagement, scientific framing sessions, and intensive working groups organized around thematic roundtables. The programme was designed to ensure a progressive transition from strategic positioning to operational co-construction.

The first day opened with participant registration and a formal institutional sequence, including the arrival of national authorities and an official opening session. This session introduced the DRC Country Package and the One Forest Vision (OFVi) initiative, highlighting their respective objectives and the role of scientific programming in supporting their implementation. It also provided an overview of ongoing structuring projects in the DRC and identified key scientific needs.

This institutional segment was followed by a series of scientific presentations illustrating existing OFVi activities, including the deployment of “super-sites”, flux towers, and capacity-building initiatives. A dedicated session was then conducted to present the methodology of the roundtables, ensuring that all participants shared a common understanding of the co-construction framework and expected outputs.

The afternoon of the first day was devoted to thematic roundtables, bringing together participants into three working groups:

- **Table A:** Climate, water, and carbon cycles
- **Table B:** Ecology and conservation (fauna, flora, ecosystems)
- **Table C:** Forestry, agriculture, and science–society interfaces

Each roundtable was facilitated by designated scientific coordinators and structured around clearly defined objectives.

The second day began with continued roundtable sessions, allowing participants to deepen discussions, refine priorities, and consolidate proposed actions. These working sessions focused on identifying key research questions, structuring potential projects, and defining associated resource and capacity needs.

The workshop concluded with a plenary restitution session, during which each roundtable presented its results. This collective synthesis enabled cross-cutting discussions, alignment between thematic areas, and the identification of complementarities. It also served as the basis for the development of a preliminary roadmap, outlining the next steps for implementing the scientific and capacity-building components of the DRC Country Package.

Overall, the programme was designed to balance institutional visibility, scientific exchange, and operational co-construction, ensuring that discussions led to concrete, structured, and actionable outcomes.

3.3. Round Tables

*Round Table A	*Round Table B	*Round Table C
<i>Climate, Water and Carbon Cycles: Challenges and Measurement Tools</i>	<i>Ecology and Conservation: Fauna, Flora and Ecosystems</i>	<i>Forestry, Agriculture and the Science-Society Link: Towards Sustainable Models</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydroclimatology and Water Resources • Wetlands and Peatlands • Carbon Cycle and Flux Towers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wildlife Conservation and Management • Study and Monitoring of Animal Biodiversity • Forest Ecology • Study and Monitoring of Plant Biodiversity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Payment for Environmental Services • Sustainability of Agricultural and Agroforestry Value Chains • Community Forestry

4. Co-Construction Workshop Methodology

The workshop was designed as a short, high-intensity co-construction process bringing together stakeholders with diverse profiles (ministries, universities, research institutes, NGOs, and international partners). The objective was not to conduct open-ended discussions, but to produce structured, actionable outputs within a limited timeframe.

To achieve this, a clear and operational methodological framework was implemented, based on three complementary tools applied sequentially during the roundtables:

4.1. Design Thinking - Structuring Needs

Each roundtable began with a Design Thinking phase aimed at anchoring discussions in concrete needs rather than abstract themes.

Participants were guided by three core questions:

- What problem needs to be solved?
- For whom? (decision-makers, local communities, scientific actors, private sector)
- What tangible benefits for the DRC?

This phase ensured that:

- priorities were demand-driven,
- discussions remained policy-relevant,
- and outputs were directly linked to national challenges and use cases.

4.2. Science Model Canvas - Structuring Projects

Once needs were clarified, discussions were structured using a Science Model Canvas, adapted to scientific programming.

Each roundtable was required to complete a standardized framework covering nine dimensions:

- Value proposition (scientific, societal, environmental)
- Beneficiaries
- Key activities
- Key resources
- Key partners
- Relations and governance

- Dissemination channels
- Cost structure
- Expected impacts

This tool ensured:

- consistency across tables,
- comparability of outputs,
- and the ability to aggregate results at plenary level.

It also forced participants to move beyond ideas and explicitly define:

- what will be done,
- with whom,
- with which resources,
- and for which outcomes.

4.3. OKR Framework - Translating into Action

The final step consisted in translating priorities into Objectives and Key Results (OKR).

For each major priority, participants were required to define:

- one clear objective,
- three to four measurable key results (maximum).

The OKR framework ensured:

- a transition from discussion to operational planning,
- measurable and trackable outputs,
- alignment with implementation timelines and funding logic.

This step was critical to:

- avoid vague or non-operational conclusions,
- structure proposals in a format compatible with donor expectations,
- and support the development of bankable project pipelines.

4.4. Expected Outputs of the Method

The methodology was designed to deliver four concrete outputs at the end of the workshop:

- **A shared vision:** Convergence on priority challenges and a common understanding of objectives.
- **Clearly defined priorities:** A limited number of robust, realistic, and policy-relevant research axes.
- **Structured OKRs:** Translation of priorities into operational objectives with measurable results.
- **An initial roadmap:** Identification of next steps, responsibilities, and resource needs for implementation.

4.5. Operational Strengths of the Approach

The strength of this methodology lies in the combination of:

- simple facilitation tools,
- rigorous structuring requirements,
- and clear, decision-oriented outputs.

It ensures that a short workshop format can produce:

- coherent scientific programming,
- aligned stakeholder engagement,

- and directly actionable results compatible with the DRC Country Package framework.

5. Results for Table A: “Climate, Water and Carbon Cycles: Issues and Measurement Tools”

5.1. Framing

The work of Table A was structured around a central question: **Where do we want to go, and with which scientific support?**

The objective is to align research questions with national priorities, in particular the structuring initiatives led by the DRC:

- the Green Corridor (Kivu–Kinshasa),
- “La Forêt c’est nous”,
- GEO-RDC.

These frameworks define a clear ambition: To articulate conservation, economic development, and sovereignty. In this context, the role of science is critical, yet remains insufficiently structured.

A key observation is the lack of operational knowledge required to support sustainable territorial valorisation and the development of local communities. This directly raises the issue of joint mobilization of research and development resources, with a focus on impact.

The guiding entry point adopted by the group is water. The water cycle provides an integrative framework linking:

- forest ecosystems,
- wetlands and peatlands,
- anthropized systems,

while bridging climate mitigation and adaptation. It also creates a direct interface between:

- scientific dimensions (Table A),
- socio-economic and governance issues (Table C).

The Green Corridor is considered a structuring study object, concentrating a wide diversity of ecosystems and challenges (biodiversity, carbon, water resources, navigation, local development). It provides a relevant framework to analyse interactions between:

- water cycle,
- ecosystem services,
- socio-economic dynamics.

5.2. Main Scientific Challenges

Several major scientific bottlenecks were identified:

- Understanding the multi-scale dynamics of the water cycle under climate change and increasing anthropogenic pressures,
- Characterizing interactions between forest ecosystem functioning, water cycles, and carbon cycles, including feedback mechanisms,
- Assessing the role of soil diversity in biogeochemical cycles.

These challenges are also embedded in a Measurement, Reporting and Verification (MRV) perspective, with a strong need for robust data on:

- emission factors,
- ecosystem dynamics (Miombo, peatlands, Green Corridor zones).

5.3. Priority Research Questions

Three main research questions were retained:

- What are the past, present, and future dynamics of the water cycle in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems of the Congo Basin and its sub-basins?
- How do forest ecosystem functions and water and carbon cycles evolve under global changes (climatic and anthropogenic), and what are the feedbacks at different scales?
- How does soil diversity influence biogeochemical cycles and the functioning of socio-ecosystems?

5.4. Participants

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Basile Mujinya Bazirake	UNILU	Professor, Department of Natural Resource Management; tropical ecosystem biogeochemistry; Miombo; geochemical cycles and carbon stocks; influence of termites on soils; Copperbelt region
Benjamin Kitambo**	CBSI / UNILU	Scientific Lead, CBSI (6 observatories); CRREBaC; hydrology; hydrogeology; space-based techniques; Lualaba wetlands
Bonaventure Lele Nyami	Agronomist / Ministry advisor	Soil management and climate change; nature-based solutions (biochar); vulnerability of agricultural systems; OFVi; <i>La Forêt c'est nous</i> programme; <i>Couloir Vert</i>
Denis Jean Sonwa	WRI	Ecologist; carbon stocks and fluxes in terrestrial ecosystems of humid forest landscapes; upscaling in the Miombo; Global Nature/Water Watch; AI
Emmanuel Kasongo Yakusu	UNIKIS	Climate; forest management; natural resource economics
Fabrice Papa**	IRD / LEGOS	Hydroclimatology; water cycle of tropical basins (Congo–Amazon); satellite hydrology; modelling
Georges-Noël Longandjo	ISTA	Professor; convective systems; evapotranspiration; vegetation heterogeneity; satellite observations
Jean-Jacques Braun	IRD	Carbon cycle and bioactive elements in rivers and wetland systems; wetlands/peatlands; hydrological cycle
Jonathan Muledi	UNILU	Director, Observatory of Open Forests; Miombo woodlands; predictive modelling for public policy
Junior Tchiteya	Environmental entrepreneur	Country Package; Forest–Climate–Nature visions; <i>Couloir Vert</i>
Laurent Kidinda	UNILU	Pedology; role of soils in C, P, and N cycles; soil carbon storage capacity
Marc Peaucelle	INRAE / ISPA	Forest macroecology; vegetation modelling; forest dynamics under global change (climate and anthropogenic drivers); biogeochemical cycles
Patience Ngelinkoto Mpia	Teacher / Ministry High. Edu. & Research.	Environmental chemistry; pollution of aquatic ecosystems; wetlands/peatlands; anthropogenic influences
Tom De Mil	Gembloux - ULiège	Forest ecology, plant ecology, climate change, natural resource management, biodiversity and conservation
Raphaël Tshimanga*	CRREBaC / UNIKIN	Hydrologist; hydrological modelling; hydro-sociology; hydroclimatology; water–energy (hydropower); blue economy; CBSI observatory

*Facilitator

** Reviewers

5.5. Value Propositions

Scientific value

- Hydrological cycle of the Congo Basin
- Spatio-temporal dynamics of water and carbon cycles
- Ecosystem functioning and feedbacks under global change (tipping points)
- Soil functioning and diversity in biogeochemical cycles
- Data production and data sovereignty

Social and policy relevance

- Development of a green economy and national sovereignty (poverty and inequality reduction)
- Community-based conservation strategies
- Navigation, energy, food security
- Adaptation, resilience, disaster and risk management
- Payment for ecosystem services (link with other tables, especially Table C)

Environmental value

- Green transition
- Climate change mitigation and biodiversity loss reduction
- Ecosystem biodiversity
- Tipping points

Beneficiaries

#	Who ?	What benefits ?
1	Local communities and populations	Well-being, water access, food security
2	Decision-makers, managers, donors	Improved knowledge of resources, decision-support tools
3	Scientific community (national and international)	Knowledge production, training, cooperation, capacity building
4	Private sector and industry	Resource quantification, ESG compliance, regulatory guidance
5	NGOs and environmental actors	Knowledge, decision support, capacity building

Key Activities

- **Axis 1: Hydroclimatology and water resources** → Hydrological processes, extreme events
- **Axis 2: Water and carbon cycles** → Stocks, lateral and vertical fluxes, greenhouse gases, wetlands and peatlands
- **Axis 3: Biogeochemical interactions** → Critical Zone functioning, socio-ecosystems, transitions and tipping points

Key Resources

Axis / Theme	Existing Resources	Needs
Axis 1 Hydroclimatology	CRREBaC, UNIKIN, UNILU labs, Ministry of Scientific Research, ISTA	laboratory equipment, infrastructure rehabilitation, MSc/PhD students (×4), hydro-meteorological stations, micro-weather stations, computing/storage capacity, IT staff (×6)
Axis 2 Water and carbon cycle	forest observatories, BEZHU UNILU, super-sites	monitoring stations, permanent plots, flux towers, automated samplers, MSc/PhD students (×4), analytical equipment, LiDAR, UAV, computing capacity, IT staff (×6)

**Axis 3
Biogeochemistry**

soil laboratories (UNIKIN, UNILU), BESET unit, EREP

flux towers, analytical equipment, LiDAR, UAV, computing capacity, MSc/PhD students (×4), IT staff (×6)

Key Partners

- **National (DRC)**
 - UNIKIN – CRREBaC
 - UNILU (BESET, OFCC)
 - UNIKIS
 - University of Kasai
 - UPN
 - INERA (Yangambi, Luki, Kipopo)
 - ICCN
 - MEDD-NEC
 - GEO-RDC
 - METTELSAT
- International
 - IRD, INRAE, CIRAD, CNRS, CEA
 - CBSI, SPCB
 - NASA, CNES, ESA
 - Universities (Leeds, UGent, Stuttgart, ULiège)
 - WRI, CIFOR-ICRAF

5.6. Relationships

- Secure all required research authorisations,
- Establish formal partnership agreements with local, national, and international institutions and stakeholders,
- Strengthen existing networks and develop new linkages among institutions and stakeholders (ministries, government agencies, donors—CAFI, EU, AFD, World Bank—private sector, NGOs, think tanks, civil society, local communities, and biodiversity and carbon consultancies),
- Ensure transparency across all collaborative activities,
- Build and sustain long-term, mutually beneficial, trust-based relationships with local communities,
- Organise thematic workshops for reflection, knowledge exchange, and feedback.

5.7. Dissemination Channels

Establish a structured communication and digital engagement plan (key events, timelines, and deliverables):

- Interdisciplinary exchanges: knowledge transfer through workshops, as well as international and sub-regional mobility,
- Scientific dissemination: peer-reviewed publications, conference presentations, and participation in scientific meetings,
- Public outreach and science communication: engagement with media and broader audiences,
- Policy-oriented communication: production of synthesis reports and evidence-based recommendations for decision-makers.

5.8. Expected Impacts

Scientific Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : Reference databases (in situ, models, satellite) • Long term : Publications, improvement of knowledge, skills development, knowledge and technology transfer
Social Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : Access to water, risk and disaster management • Long term : Well-being, resilience, adaptation
Policy Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : Contributions to decision-making and public policies, policy briefs • Long term : Better knowledge of resources, decision-support tools, policy briefs
Climate Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : Carbon balance • Long term : Development and production of indicators
Ecosystem Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : Conservation, restoration • Long term : RAMSAR designation

5.9. OKR: Objectives and Key Results

Table A defined its three objectives in alignment with the priority frameworks: La Forêt c'est nous, the Couloir Vert, and GEO RDC.

Axis 1	
Hydroclimatology of the Congo Basin and water resources / extreme events	
KR1	<p>Establishment of “hydroclimatic stations” across six sub-basins of the Congo Basin</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kisangani (Forests) • Ankoro (Miombo ecosystems) • Kutu-Moké / Kasai (Forest-Savanna ecosystems) • Mbandaka (Forests) • Bolobo (Humid forests, peatlands) • Lokolela (Wetlands, peatlands) • Inga (downstream of the basin) • Mangroves
KR2	<p>Measurements and modelling</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lateral fluxes: carbon, sediments, biogeochemistry, • Vertical fluxes: greenhouse gases (GHGs), • Meteorological measurements: precipitation, latent heat, • Satellite observations: SWOT, TRISHNA, Biomass, GEO RDC, • Modelling and data mining.
KR3	<p>Creation and Strengthening of Laboratories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geomatics, information technology, and analytical platforms, • Target laboratories: Kisangani, Kinshasa, University of Lubumbashi (UniLu), and Mbuji-Mayi (Kasai), in relation to the main ecosystem zones.
KR4	<p>Capacity Building</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 geomatics/IT engineers and technicians • 5 PhD theses/post-docs • 30 masters • Continuing training (3/year)

Axis 2	
Water and carbon cycles (stocks, lateral and vertical fluxes), greenhouse gases (GHGs), peatlands, and forested wetlands	
KR1	<p>Ecosystems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Miombo: Kaboué, Kitakia, Sakanya, CFCL (Community Forest Concessions), • Forest–savanna ecosystem: to be defined in collaboration with the University, • Humid forest / peatland ecosystem: CBSI sites (to be discussed), • Permanent plots (prioritising GEO-TREES).
KR2	<p>Equipment and modelling</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flux towers and carbon stock measurements: Miombo, Yangambi (currently the only operational site), swamps (Lokolama), • Modelling and remote sensing.
KR3	<p>Creation and Strengthening of Laboratories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical platforms, IT • Target laboratories: Kisangani, Kinshasa, University of Lubumbashi (UniLu), and Mbuji-Mayi (Kasai)
KR4	<p>Capacity Building</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 IT/geomatics engineers and technicians (including 2 dedicated to the Miombo), • 5 PhD and postdoctoral positions (estimated), • 30 Master’s students.

Axis 3	
Interactions among biogeochemical cycles, Critical Zone functioning, socio-ecosystems, transitions, and tipping points	
KR1	<p>Ecosystems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Miombo; forest–savanna ecosystem: to be defined in collaboration with the University, • Humid forest / peatland ecosystem: CBSI sites (to be discussed), • Mangrove (site), swamps (Lokolama), • Permanent plots (prioritising GEO-TREES).
KR2	<p>Equipment and modelling</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flux towers, vertical fluxes • Biogeochemical cycles (C, N, P) / soil / vegetation • Modelling / satellites • Permanent plots
KR3	<p>Creation and Strengthening of Laboratories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 institutions / complementarity / pooling / encouraging intra-country mobility • Analytical platforms, IT
KR4	<p>Capacity Building</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 IT/geomatics engineers and technicians • 5 supervised theses (encourage intra-country co-supervision) • 30 masters

5.10. Cost Structure

See annex 3 for the cost categories to consider

5.11. Roadmap — Next Steps

Short term (0–6 mois)	Medium term (6–18 months)	Long term (18 mois & au-delà)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative procedures: authorisation of the Miombo supersite (GEO-TREES, flux tower), • Call for projects (PhD theses) and student recruitment, • Inter-institutional outreach and equipment inventory, • Identification of potential donors, • Establishment of the Country Committee, • Establishment of working groups (to be discussed in plenary), • Data mining and development of a data management plan. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of flux towers and initiation of data acquisition, • Launch of PhD projects, • Communication management (including monitoring indicators), • Engagement with potential donors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data collection and analysis, • Thesis supervision, committees, and defences.

6. Results for Table B: “Ecology and Conservation: Fauna, Flora and Habitats”

The work of Table B is structured around a central question: **How can biodiversity in the DRC be better understood and preserved, while addressing national priorities and the needs of local communities?**

A key observation is that the lack of operational knowledge limits the capacity to sustainably valorise territories and support local development. This highlights the need to jointly mobilise resources for research and development, with a clear focus on tangible impact.

The guiding framework adopted is the assessment of biodiversity at the national scale, structured along four complementary axes:

- **Biodiversity assessment:**
 - Analysis across taxa (flora, fauna, microorganisms),
 - Study of interaction networks (symbioses, trophic chains, etc.),
 - Characterisation of ecosystems (forests, wetlands, savannas, peatlands, etc.),
- **Drivers of change and management approaches:**
 - Identification of anthropogenic and natural pressures affecting biodiversity,
 - Development of tools to monitor and document these changes (monitoring systems, indicators, databases),
 - Design of adapted management approaches integrating local knowledge and public policies,
- **Organismal responses to global change:**
 - Analysis of forest ecology and species resilience to climate variability and disturbances,
 - Assessment of ecosystem vulnerability and adaptation mechanisms,
- **Ecosystem services and human well-being:**
 - Strengthening the links between biodiversity and health (zoonoses, food security, nutrition),
 - Evaluation of key ecosystem services (climate regulation, water provision, pollination),
 - Integration of climate considerations into conservation and development strategies.

These axes are embedded within a monitoring and quantification framework, with a strong requirement for robust data on ecosystem dynamics and pressure factors. The objective is to structure

a coherent scientific framework capable of informing public policy, supporting national initiatives, and strengthening the science–development–policy interface.

Four main research questions emerge:

- What is the current state and trajectory of biodiversity at the national scale across taxa, interaction networks, and ecosystem types?
- What are the main drivers of biodiversity change, and which tools are needed to monitor and manage them sustainably?
- How do organisms and ecosystems respond to global change, and which adaptation and resilience mechanisms should be prioritised?
- What are the links between biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human well-being, and how can these be integrated into conservation and development policies?

These elements provide a foundation for structuring research priorities, observation systems, and operational actions within national and international programmes.

6.1. Participants

First Name / Last Name	Institution	Specialty / Field
Bhely Angoboy Ilondea	INERA	Forest ecology, agronomy, soil management, biodiversity, phenology, climatology, biosphere reserve management (notably the Luki Biosphere Reserve)
Célestin Danadu	UNIKIS - CSB	Ichthyology and biodiversity
Dav Ebengo	INOHA	OneHealth, remote sensing, soil sciences, forest ecology, natural resource management, environmental modelling
Jean-Christophe Bokika Ngawolo	Mbou-Mon-Tour	Community conservation, bonobo ecology, protected area management, ancestral knowledge and biodiversity
Jean-Francois Bastin	Gembloux - ULiège	Ecology, remote sensing, drones, ecosystem restoration, climate change
Jean Remy Makana	UNIKIS & WCS	Tropical forest ecology, biodiversity, forest management, carbon sequestration, REDD+
Jean Semeki Ngabinzeke	UNIKIN - FacAgro	Integrated forest management, ecology, biodiversity, ecosystem services
Jérôme Chave *	CNRS - CRBE	Tropical forest ecology, biodiversity, ecosystem modelling, biogeochemistry, remote sensing, forest response to climate change
John Katembo	UNKIS	Forest ecology, remote sensing and sustainable forest management
Mylor Ngoy Shutcha	UNILU - FacAgro	Plant ecology, ecological restoration, ecosystem services, agroforestry, sustainable soil management
Nicolas Barbier **	IRD - AMAP	Forest ecology, phenology, remote sensing, drones
Tom De Mil	Gembloux - ULiège	Forest ecology, plant ecology, climate change, natural resource management, biodiversity and conservation
Vivien Rossi **	CIRAD	Forest dynamics models, natural resource assessment
Yannick Useni Sikuzani	UNILU - FacAgro	Urban ecology, landscape ecology, plant ecology, remote sensing, landscape sustainability

*Facilitator

** Reviewers

6.2. Value Propositions

Scientific Value

- State of biodiversity at the national level, for different taxa, interaction networks and ecosystem types,
- Drivers of biodiversity change (land use, exploitation, climate) and the means to document them,
- Response of organisms and ecosystems to global changes, particularly in forest environments,
- Links between biodiversity and ecosystem services (health, food, climate).

Social and policy relevance

- Knowledge of the state of natural resources,
- Resource and ecosystem service management strategies,
- Alignment with international commitments (biodiversity and climate), including biodiversity and carbon credit mechanisms,
- Sustainable economic development and improvement of living conditions.

Environmental Value

- Ecosystem conservation strategies,
- Strengthening the resilience of socio-ecosystems in the face of global changes,
- Ecological and economic valorisation of ecosystems.

6.3. Beneficiaries

#	Who ?	What benefits ?
1	Local communities and indigenous peoples (IPLC) and Congolese citizens as a whole	Valorisation of knowledge about their resources, support for their sustainable management
2	Political decision-makers & public administration	Poverty reduction and well-being, decision-support tools and public policy guidance
3	Private sector	Environmentally responsible economic development and improvement of value chains
4	Scientific and academic communities	Capacity building for researchers and faculty; enhanced connectivity between institutions; increased international visibility. Strengthening laboratories and centres of excellence to better host and retain early-career researchers after their PhDs..
5	Humanity and the Planet	Protection of ecosystems and biodiversity, global resources, environmental justice

6.4. Key Activities

- **Axis 1: State of Animal and Plant Biodiversity.**
 - Strengthening the network of long-term biodiversity monitoring super-sites (fauna and flora) in different ecosystems, in coordination with international initiatives (Geo-Trees, Canobs),
 - Involvement of local communities in observation systems,
 - Establishment of a biodiversity data analysis and synthesis centre,
 - Strengthening and modernisation of national biological collections (herbaria, zoological collections), including their digitisation and interoperability with international databases.
- **Axis 2: Drivers of Biodiversity Change**
 - Conducting an updated national forest inventory (NFI),
 - Analysis of land use changes over the past ten years,
 - Assessment of forest degradation in relation to management practices.
- **Axis 3: Organismal Response to Global Changes**
 - Analysis of the effects of hunting and agriculture on biodiversity involving communities,
 - Study of the response of plant species (particularly trees) to climate and anthropogenic changes.
- **Axis 4: Understanding Ecosystem Services**
 - Assessment of ecosystem services (food, health, energy, economy),
 - Développement d'approches interdisciplinaires en lien avec les sciences humaines et sociales.
- **Cross-Cutting Approaches**

- Development of participatory science, notably through the deployment and training of automatic recognition tools (Pl@ntNet type) adapted to local floras,
- Integration of these approaches into monitoring systems, including through drone acquisitions (RGB, multispectral images) and LiDAR,
- Coordination between field observations, reference collections, and remote sensing data.

6.5. Key Resources

Axis / Theme	Existing Resources	Needs
Axe 1 State of Animal and Plant Biodiversity	Localised sites (see Annex 2); MEDD platform	Super-site equipment, rehabilitation of biological collections, training, mobility grants, master/PhD students, IT staff
Axis 2 Drivers of biodiversity change	Localised sites (see Annex 2), First national forest inventory, Remote sensing data	Super-site equipment, second national forest inventory, dedicated staff
Axis 3 Organismal Response to Global Changes	Localised sites (see Annex 2); ongoing experiments (CanObs)	Strengthening and long-term maintenance of sites, training
Axis 4 Understanding ecosystem services	Remote sensing data, Initiatives: <i>Couloir Vert</i> and ongoing pilot projects, MpoxProbe, research projects funded by Belgian cooperation, OneHealth Preserve, etc.	Pathogen monitoring system, analytical equipment for resource monitoring, training, master/PhD students, IT staff

6.6. Key Partners

DRC: National Institutions

- Universities and research centres (UNIKIN, UNIKIS, UNILU, INOHA, INERA)
- Technical services and sectoral ministries
- Observatoire Satellital des Forêts d'Afrique Centrale (OSFAC)

International Partners

- Regional networks (COMIFAC, RIFFEAC, R2FAC, OFAC)
- Scientific initiatives (OFVi, CBSI, SPCB)
- International universities and research centres
- GEO (GEO TREES, GEO BON, etc)
- Technical and financial partners

6.7. Relationships

- Obtain the necessary agreements from competent authorities.
- Establish partnerships with civil society organisations (CSOs), the private sector, local communities and indigenous peoples, as well as NGOs specialised in conservation and natural resource management.
- Create synergies between these stakeholders for an integrated and inclusive approach.
- Ensure clear and equitable communication in all collaborations.
- Establish reflection and feedback workshops to promote dialogue and co-construction.

6.8. Dissemination Channels

A dissemination plan will be implemented to reach different audiences through:

- Scientific publications: peer-reviewed articles, reports, and synthesis documents,
- Conferences and events: presentations at conferences, seminars, and thematic meetings,
- Policy briefs: targeted policy notes for decision-makers,
- Feedback workshops: stakeholder meetings to share results and collect feedback,

- Institutional platforms: integration of results into databases and official reports,
- Digital channels: dissemination to both public and professional audiences via websites and social media.

6.9. Expected Impacts

Scientific Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : consolidation and synthesis of existing data, • Long term : improvement of knowledge and structuring of a national biodiversity observation system.
Social Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : better consideration of resources in local policies, • Long term : improvement of well-being and livelihoods.
Policy Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : decision support and production of policy briefs, • Long term : integration of biodiversity into public policies.
Climate Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : better understanding of biodiversity–climate links, • Long term : contribution to mitigation and adaptation strategies.
Ecosystem Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : improvement of conservation practices, • Long term : restoration and maintenance of ecosystems.

6.10. OKR: Objectives and Key Results

Axis 1	
Study and Monitoring of Animal Biodiversity et végétale	
KR1	Creation and/or Strengthening of Sites
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of super-sites representative of major ecosystems (infrastructure & equipment renewal, human resources support, coordination monitoring) • Integration with GEO-TREES / CanObs • Deployment of integrated systems combining: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ permanent plots (flora) including herbaceous plants ○ fauna monitoring including insects ○ drones (RGB + multispectral) ○ LiDAR (UAV + terrestrial) • Acquisition of standardised time series
KR2	National Synthesis
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish a “synthesis centre” to provide a structured framework for addressing targeted research questions, potentially hosted across multiple institutions, • Conduct a comprehensive synthesis of existing literature, • Map stakeholders producing data (metadata catalogue, with support from data analysts), • Foster collaboration among Congolese researchers to contribute to the platform and engage with the synthesis centre (including intra-country mobility grants), • Rehabilitate biological collections (herbaria, reference collections) and support their digitisation.
KR3	Capacity Building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training of super-site staff and researchers (systematics, data analysis, ...) • Engineers and technicians • Supervised theses and masters on super-sites

Axis 2 Drivers of biodiversity change and organismal responses to global change	
KR1	<p>Creation and/or Strengthening of Sites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish continuous monitoring on sites with different management approaches and along an anthropisation gradient • Production of a national biodiversity baseline (flora, fauna, habitats)
KR2	<p>National Synthesis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finalise the second national forest inventory (field + lidar) • Mapping of land use changes (10–20 years) • Assessment of forest degradation and fragmentation • Analysis of pressures (hunting, agriculture, exploitation) by integrating communities to raise awareness • Identification of sensitive areas / biodiversity tipping points • Development of biodiversity–land use–climate models • Production of development scenarios to support public policies
KR3	<p>Capacity Building</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dedicated staff for monitoring and interpreting management-related trends • Establishment of national storage, computing and database management capacity

Axis 3 Understanding ecosystem services	
KR1	<p>Assessment of Ecosystem Services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantification of services related to food, health (zoonoses), climate, and energy, • Mapping of ecosystem services at the national scale / <i>Couloir Vert</i>, • Pilot demonstrator project (living lab approach) including monitoring of pathogens and vectors under a One Health framework, and monitoring of energy resources (fuelwood).
KR2	<p>Integration into Public Policies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National-scale measurement of the impacts of hunting on biodiversity • Production of biodiversity policy briefs • Contribution to national frameworks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ carbon / biodiversity credits ○ territorial planning ○ conservation strategies
KR3	<p>Development of Sustainable Value Chains</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of biodiversity-compatible sectors • Support for the structuring of local value chains • Private sector integration

6.11. Cost Structure

See annex 3 for the cost categories to consider

6.12. Roadmap — Next Steps

Short term (0–6 mois)	Medium term (6–18 months)	Long term (18 mois & au-delà)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OFVi call for projects to support complete PhD theses • Support for thesis completion (6 months - 1 year - 2 years) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch of OFVi projects • Approaching other donors • Inventory of ongoing initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term maintenance of monitoring systems • Scientific and operational valorisation of data

- Site inventory for a super-site application to GEO-TREES
- Renforcement de la plateforme (mobilités & data analyst)
- Structuring of an integrated national biodiversity observation network

7. Results for Table C: “ Forestry, Agriculture and the Science-Society Link: Towards Sustainable Models ”

The work of Table C distinguished and addressed three themes:

- **Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES)**
- **Sustainable Value Chains**
- **Community Forestry.**

The discussions took place sequentially following this framework:

- Current state of activities and research in DRC
- Identification of relevant but under-addressed research questions
- Collective prioritisation of 2-4 relevant research questions on the sub-theme.

7.1. Participants

First Name / Last Name	Institution	Specialty / Field
Alphonse Maindo	UNIKIS	Political science, forest governance, post-conflict reconstruction, natural resource management, environmental policy, democracy and development, human rights
Bhely Angoboy Ilondea	INERA	Forest ecology, agronomy, soil management, biodiversity, phenology, climatology, biosphere reserve management (notably the Luki Biosphere Reserve)
Bonaventure Lélé Nyami	UNIKIN - FacAgro	Natural resource management, agroforestry, ecology, environmental degradation, firewood exploitation
Caroline Coulon	IRD	One Health, research project coordination, virology, epidemiology, global health
David Badesire Willy	CIFOR	Monitoring and evaluation (MEL), programme quality, project management
Dieu-Merci Assumani Angbonda	INERA	Evolutionary biology, forest ecology, seedling and nursery management, forest ecosystem dynamics
Donesfort Masuki Matuba	INERA	Biosphere reserve management (notably the Luki Biosphere Reserve), biodiversity
Emmanuel Kasongo	UNIKIN	Political and administrative sciences, governance of decentralised territorial entities, local public finances, decentralisation
Guillaume Lescuyer *	CIRAD - CIFOR	Ecological economics, forest socio-economics, sustainable management of tropical forests, economic value of forests, forest policies
Jean Semeki Ngabinzeke	UNIKIN - FacAgro	Integrated forest management, ecology, biodiversity, ecosystem services
Lucie Temgoua **	ERAIFT	Forestry, agroforestry, ecology of forest and agroforestry ecosystems, biodiversity dynamics, socio-economic and ecological analysis of tree plantations
Pitchou Tshimpanga Ongona	UNIKIS - CIFOR	Resource economics, supply chain management, environmental economics, artisanal timber exploitation, forest public policies
Salomon Mampeta Wabasa	UNIKIS	Community Forestry, gouvernance
Serge Kalawu Mangala	AFD	Monitoring and evaluation (MEL), programme quality, project management, REDD+

*Facilitator

**Reviewers

7.2. Value Propositions

Scientific Value

- In-depth understanding of payment for environmental services mechanisms and their impact on local communities.
- Development of Sustainable Value Chains pour les produits forestiers et agricoles.
- Effective and equitable community forestry models.

Social and Policy Relevance

- Improvement of local communities' livelihoods.
- Strengthening of public policies for sustainable resource management.
- Integration of local knowledge into management mechanisms.

Environmental Value

- Reduction of deforestation and forest degradation.
- Conservation of biodiversity and ecosystem services.
- Promotion of sustainable agricultural and forestry practices.

7.3. Beneficiaries

Idem Tables A et B

7.4. Key Activities

- **Theme 1: Payments for Environmental Services (PES)**
 - Study of the impacts of PES on sustainable development trajectories.
 - Analysis of governance mechanisms and legal frameworks.
 - Assessment of endogenous knowledge and commodification risks.
- **Theme 2 : Sustainable Value Chains (SVC)**
 - Analysis of the impacts of infrastructure on value chain efficiency.
 - Development of reference frameworks for sustainable products.
 - Study of financing and certification models.
- **Theme 3 : Community Forestry**
 - Assessment of the contributions of local community forest concessions (LCFC) to environmental services.
 - Development of profitable and equitable economic models.
 - Integration of LCFCs into national sustainable development policies.

7.5. Key Resources

Theme	Existing Resources in DRC	Needs / Requests
Theme 1 Payments for ecosystem services (PES)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ibi plantations on the Batéké Plateaux; FONAREDD; provincial PIREDD programmes; CAFI PES schemes; JICA projects in Kwilu; REDD+ initiatives, • Future plantations under the TFFF and Z3D initiatives, and CAFI calls for proposals (including a methodological package), • Attempted biodiversity PES schemes by Jeff Dupain, FRMi, and the Antwerp Zoo. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of the sustainability and effectiveness of PES schemes, and their impacts on industrial sectors, • Clarification of local governance arrangements and stakeholder roles (NGOs, donors), • Identification of appropriate legal and institutional frameworks to ensure PES accessibility for IPLCs, • Natural capital accounting and equitable benefit-sharing mechanisms,

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determination of relevant scales (local, regional, national) and identification of effective recipient platforms.
<p>Theme 2 Sustainable Value Chains</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Occasional studies on certain sectors (cassava, maize) around protected areas or sites • Some companies engaged in sustainability certification • Study on agroecology (ENABEL) with support from the Minister of Agriculture • Ministry of Research Platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study of perennial crops (cocoa, coffee, palm) or more local ones (honey, caterpillar, rattan) or for national sectors • Study of product processing • Digitisation of existing data
<p>Theme 3 Community Forestry</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numerous LCFC experiences in the majority of provinces (financial costs and economic profitability) • Ongoing evaluations of the five-year experimental phase by the DFC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study of sustainability after the end of support • Continued technical and legal support for mitigation of internal conflicts and with mining titles • Assessment of the impact of LCFCs • Improve the legal and operational framework (harmonisation, traceability, clarification of roles) • Integration of LCFCs into public policies

7.6. Key Partners

DRC: National Institutions

- Universities and research centres (UNIKIN, UNIKIS, INERA)
- Technical services and sectoral ministries

International Partners

- Regional networks (CIFOR-ICRAF, R2FAC, RESSAC)
- International universities and research centres
- Technical and financial partners

7.7. Relationships

- Collaboration with local communities and institutional stakeholders.
- Partnerships with the private sector for the development of sustainable value chains.
- Capacity Building et échange de connaissances.

7.8. Dissemination Channels

- Scientific publications and reports.
- Feedback workshops and seminars.
- Digital platforms and media.

7.9. Expected Impacts

Scientific Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : Consolidation of data and knowledge on PES, value chains and community forestry. • Long term : Improvement of management models and development of new approaches.
Social Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : Strengthening of community resilience and autonomy. • Long term : Improvement of living conditions of local communities.
Policy Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : Decision-making support and development of public policies. • Long term : Integration of sustainable approaches into national strategies.
Climate Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : Contribution to national and international climate objectives. • Long term : Reduction of carbon emissions and improvement of sequestration.
Ecosystem Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term : Improvement of natural resource management. • Long term : Conservation and restoration of ecosystems.

7.10. Priority Research Questions

Theme 1 Payments for Environmental Services (PES)	
QR1	What are the impacts of PES mechanisms on the medium- and long-term (sustainable) development trajectories of the territories where they are implemented?
QR2	Will industrial timber production in the DRC withstand the expansion of carbon and biodiversity PES schemes?

Theme 2 Sustainable Value Chains	
QR1	Characteristics and utility of a reference framework for sustainable agroforestry cocoa
QR2	How do infrastructure and the institutional framework influence the efficiency of sustainable value chains?
QR3	Characterisation and promotion of national demand for legal and sustainable agricultural, agroforestry and forest products

Theme 3 Community Forestry	
QR1	How can CFCLs be integrated into national sustainable development policies and national/regional land-use planning frameworks?
QR2	Which CFCL business models are genuinely profitable and equitable for IPLCs?
QR3	What are the contributions of CFCLs to the maintenance of global ecosystem services (climate regulation, biodiversity conservation, etc.), and do they outperform other forest management models?
QR4	Which mechanisms and safeguards are needed to enable direct access by local communities and Indigenous peoples to financing that supports their CFCLs?

7.11. Cost Structure

See annex 3 for the cost categories to consider

7.12. Roadmap — Next Steps

Short term (0–6 mois)	Medium term (6–18 months)	Long term (18 mois & au-delà)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decision on the scientific themes to be promoted by OFVi-DRC • Launch of the call for tenders to mobilise Congolese-French 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Start of support for complete, impulse or finalisation PhD theses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Award and public defence of complete PhD theses

scientific groups on the
selected themes

- Selection of scientific themes
and definition of support
modalities

8. Annexes

8.1. Annex 1: Location of Table A Sites

Figure 1. Map of the Congo Basin showing sub-basins and major associated ecosystem types, the Central Cuvette, the boundaries of the Democratic Republic of the Congo, the Couloir Vert (Virunga–Kinshasa), and the location of hydro-meteorological supersites.

8.2. Annex 2: Location of Table B Sites

Site name	Associated institutions	Main ecosystem	Boarding Lodging	Security	Animal survey (Camera-traps, ADNe ...)	Presence of forest inventories (date of the most recent inventory)	Airborne optical monitoring (dates)	TLS (terrestrial laser scanning) (dates)	Meteorological station	Additional experiments	Scientific visibility (publications)
Babagulu	Université de Kisangani (UNIKIS), Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale (MRAC) & Université de Gand (UGent)	Monodominant forest of <i>Gilbertiodendron dewevrei</i>	No/acceptable	Yes	Planned	Six permanent monitoring systems established in 2024	Planned	No	No		Kabuanga et al 2020 (doi:10.4000/vertigo.28347)
Baego	UGent, MRAC	Dense humid forest and secondary forests	No	Yes	No	Yes, 2022		No			
Bolobo/MMT CFCL-RM	UICN/PPI, Mbou-Mon-Tour, AFD/ProBio dev, Fondation Arcus, WWF, Synchronicity Earth, Bonobo Eco, Bonobo jeans, Bonobo World, Play Nature, RFN, PNUD/SGP/gef/ IKI, Agroecology Fund,	Mixed dense forest; secondary–primary gradient; forest–savanna mosaic	Available	No issues	Daily monitoring and habituation of bonobos by tracker teams (Mbou-Mon-Tour)	Conducted by World Wide Fund for Nature in 2006; yes (2020)	Yes (8,000 ha covered by optical surveys in 2015 – World Wide Fund for Nature / NASA)	Yes (8,000 ha covered by optical surveys in 2015 – World Wide Fund for Nature / NASA)	Not yet	Potential CANOBS protocol	Mémoires & thèses de doctorat https://esajournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1890/13-1574.1 https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0142146 https://www.nature.com/articles/srep13156 https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-017-15050-z https://royalsocietypublishing.org/rstb/article/368/1625/20120295/22266 https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/ajp.22425 https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0093742 https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S006320716303275 Forestplots.net GFBI CafriplotsR

	Sounds Right, ULiege, MNHN....										
Djolu	UGent, MRAC, UNIKIS	Dense humid forest	Yes	Yes	No	Yes, 2024		No	No		
Ituri	UNIKIS, ForestGEO, WCS	<i>Gilbertiodendron</i> forest and mixed forest	Yes	Problématique		Yes, 2016	Yes	Yes	No		Hart et al 1989, Hart 1990, Hart 1995, Makana et al 2011, Ewango et al 2015, Glick et al 2021, Glick et al 2023
Kafubu											
Kundelungu	UNILU, ULiege	Open Miombo woodland	Yes	Yes	Sherman traps; camera traps	Yes	No	No	No	Activities – inventories – under the PRD BiSHaK project (monitoring and prevention of zoonotic risks linked to wildlife) The PRD BiSHaK project is embedded in a One Health approach and aims to strengthen surveillance and prevention of zoonotic risks at the human–animal–ecosystem	http://orcid.org/0000-0001-7366-3647 ; https://doi.org/10.3390/fire6050174 ; https://doi.org/10.15451/10.15451/ec2020-08-9.33-1-9

											interface, particularly in the Haut-Katanga region.	
Lokoloma												
Lomani N	Institut Congolais pour la Conservation de la Nature (ICCN), UNIKIS, MRAC, University of Leeds	Dense humid forest; seasonally flooded forest	No	Issues	Yes	Yes, 2025	No	No	Yes			Kompanyi et al 2025 (doi:10.1111/ddi.70118)
Lomani S	ICCN, UNIKIS, MRAC, University of Leeds	Dense humid forest; seasonally flooded forest	No	Issues	Yes	Yes, 2026	No	No	Yes			Kompanyi et al 2025 (doi:10.1111/ddi.70118)
Lubumbashi Mikembo												
Luki	INERA, ULiege, UGent	Mayombe forest	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes (2025)	Yes (every two weeks since late 2023)	Yes (2023, 2025)	Yes	Phenocams, dendrometers, CANOBS protocol		Many
Mabali	ULiege, CREF	Mixed dense forest; secondary–primary gradient; terra firme and flooded forests; peatlands	Yes	Yes	?	Yes (2026)	Yes (every two weeks since early 2026)	Yes (2025)	No	CANOBS protocol		New site on the shore of Lake Tumba
Mushima/région de Kolwezi	UNIKOL, ULiege, Ministère provincial de l'environnement	Open Miombo woodland; dry dense forest; gallery forest	Yes	Yes	No	Yes (from June 2026 onward)	Yes (from June 2022–2023 onward)	No	Yes, at Kolwezi Airport	Activities under the Amorce ARBORE KOL project		https://doi.org/10.3390/conservation6020048 ; https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5561496 ; https://doi.org/10.3390/rs16203903

Mwawa/région de Lubumbashi	UNILU, ULiège, UCLouvain	Open Miombo woodland	Yes	No	No	Yes, 2022	Yes, in 2022-2023	No	No	Activities / forest inventories with permanent plots under the PRD CHARLU project	https://doi.org/10.3390/su152014943 ; https://doi.org/10.3390/geographies6010024 ; https://doi.org/10.3390/ecologies6010017 ; https://doi.org/10.3390/f14040687
Rubi-Tele	UCCN, UNIKIS (CSB)	Monodominant <i>Gilbertiodendron dewevrei</i> forest and mixed forest	No/acceptable	Yes	Routine work in a hunting concession	Multi-date inventory (2015–2025); ichthyological inventory conducted in 2009 (unpublished report)	No	No	No	No	http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1215909
Salonga N	Salonga Conservation Initiative (SCI), UNIKIS, MRAC	<i>Gilbertiodendron dewevrei</i> and mixed forests	Yes, tents and wooden house accommodation	No issues to report	Yes, camera traps, transects, and direct observations	Yes (2025: 13 plots of 1 ha, including 9 on terra firme and 4 in seasonally flooded forest)	No	No	Yes	Effect of trees 'basal area and substrate on the regeneration in the Rubi Tele Domaine de Chasse mature forest. Revue Scientifique et Technique Forêt et Environnement du Bassin du Congo, Volume 13. P. 12-20, Octobre (2019), Print ISSN : 2409-1693/ Online ISSN : 2412-3005	
Salonga S	Max-Planck-Institute of Animal Behavior, 78465 Konstanz, Université de Konstanz, ICCN, UNIKIN/CeRFoB, INRB	Evergreen dense humid forest of the Central Cuvette (primary), with a secondary-degraded gradient in some areas	Yes, tents and wooden house accommodation	Yes	Yes: line transects, camera traps, acoustic traps, direct observations, and hunting effort monitoring	Monthly phenology monitoring; comparison of two sites since 2022; herbarium at UNIKIN (INERA)	No, not yet	No No, not yet	Yes, present at the LuiKotale camp	Plant and animal biodiversity; plant-animal interactions; humans as an integral component of the ecosystem	Yes, we have good scientific visibility through our publications. Not all outputs originate strictly from the SNP study area, but they can be filtered using the following links: https://www.ab.mpg.de/publication-search/342195?person=%2Fpersons%2Fresource%2Fpersons203308 https://www.eva.mpg.de/ecology/staff/hohmann/#c34924 https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8066-6413 For a clearer overview of the study site and our activities, the following resources are particularly relevant: 1. https://www.ab.mpg.de/364649/fruth 2. https://salonga.org/field-stories/the-luikotale-bonobo-research-story/ 3. https://www.eva.mpg.de/procuv/
Uma	ISEA BENGAMIS	Monodominant forests	No	Yes	No	Multi-date	No	No	No	Herbarium	Forests 2020, 11, 0; doi:10.3390/f11050000

	A, AMAP - IRD	of <i>Gilbertiodendron dewevrei</i> and <i>Julbernardia seretii</i> , and mixed forest				inventory (2015–2025)					
Yangambi	ULiege, UGent, INERA, UNIKIS, UCCN, Unikis (CSB), UE, UNESCO	Mixed dense forest; secondary–primary gradient	Yes	OK (but challenging due to the Kisangani airport)	Several (ongoing PhD theses)	Yes (2026)	Yes (every two weeks since late 2023)	Yes (2015, 2023)	Yes (since 1933)	Flux tower; herbarium	Many 10.111/jfb. 14226. En
Yoko	UNIKIS (CSB), Cirad, MRAC, UCCN	Dense humid forest and secondary forests	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes, 2025	No	No			Umunay et al 2017, Hubau et al 2020, Forestplots.net , Etudes phénologiques et dispersion des fruits de <i>Guarea cedrata</i> et <i>Guarea thompsonii</i> (Meliaceae) dans les forêts semi-caducifoliées du massifs forestier de Kisangani (RDC). <i>Geo-Eco-Trop.</i> , 2021, 45, 1 : 145-159; http://www.geocotrop.be

8.3. Annex 3: Cost Categories to Consider for Cost Structuring

1	Personnel	Salaires et avantages sociaux des chercheurs principaux, collaborateurs et personnel de soutien ; formation et développement professionnel ; recrutement de PhD, post-docs, IT et gestionnaires de projets
2	Equipment	Purchase or rental of specialised equipment
3	Infrastructure	Renovation of existing laboratories and research stations (super-sites)
4	Consumables	Laboratory materials, office supplies, chemicals, etc.
5	Travel and Accommodation	Conferences, collaborator meetings, fieldwork or laboratory
6	Communication	Access to databases, specialised journals, software subscriptions
7	Administrative Costs	Management, legal and accounting services
8	Subcontracting	Purchase of specialised services
9	Results Dissemination	Publications, organisation of conferences
10	Evaluation and Monitoring	Progress monitoring and project evaluation